

Lakota Religious Traditions

By Ryan Goeckner, University of Kansas Medical Center

Entry tags: Religious Group, Native American (North American) Religions, Lakota Religious Traditions

The Lakota people are the westernmost members of the Očhéthi Šakówiŋ (Seven Council Fires). Primarily a linguistic designation, Lakota people are made up of a variety of different thiyóšpaye (bands) and today reside on the Cheyenne River, Pine Ridge, Standing Rock, and Rosebud reservations in western North and South Dakota as well as in various off-reservation communities around the United States. The goal of this entry is to focus primarily on the practice of Lakota religious traditions from the beginning of the reservation era to the present (2018). Membership in this group is primarily determined by acceptance within the community, however colonial policies of blood quantum continue to be imposed by the United States federal government, alongside other American Indian communities, complicating who may or may not be considered a legitimate practitioner of Lakota religion by other Lakotas. Additionally, political membership within Lakota communities does not guarantee any given individual's personal practice of these traditions because various Christian denominations continue to be practiced in these on and off-reservation communities.

Date Range: 1889 CE - 2018 CE

Region: Lakota Reservations 2

Region tags: North America, United States of America

Current Lakota Reservations

Status of Participants:

✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Goodman, Ronald. *Lakota Star Knowledge: Studies in Lakota Stellar Theology*. Rosebud: Sinte Gleska University, 1992.
- Source 2: Hassrick, Royal B. *The Sioux; Life and Customs of a Warrior Society. The Civilization of the American Indian Series.*, 1st ed. Norman,: University of Oklahoma Press, 1964.
- Source 3: Lebeau, Sebastian. "Reconstructing Lakota Ritual in the Landscape: The Identification and Typing System for Traditional Cultural Property Sites." Dissertation, University of Minnesota, 2009.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: Buechel, Eugene. *Lakota Tales & Texts*. Edited by Paul Manhart. Chamberlain, S.D.: Tipi Press, 1998.
- Source 2: Buechel, Eugene, and Paul Manhart. *Lakota Dictionary : Lakota-English/English-Lakota*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 2002.
- Source 3: Costello, Damian. "Black Elk : Colonialism and Lakota Catholicism." Maryknoll, N.Y.: Orbis Books,

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: Crow, Fools. "Fools Crow." edited by Thomas E. Mails, D. Chief Eagle, Dallas Chief Eagle and D. Chief Eagle. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1990.
- Source 2: Davis, L. "The Socio-Cultural Changes in the Cheyenne River Sioux Indians as a Result of Contact with White Civilization." Thesis, University of Southern California, 1944.
- Source 3: Deloria, Ella Cara. Speaking of Indians. Edited by Agnes Picotte and Paul N. Pavich. Vermillion: Dakota Press, 1979.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: Goeckner, Ryan . ""These Type of Sites are Really Hard to Find": Lakota Oral Tradition and Resistance Against the Dakota Access Pipeline." Thesis, University of Kansas, 2018.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: Montileaux, Donald F., and South Dakota State Historical Society. Tatanka and the Lakota People : A Creation Story. 1 vols. Pierre, S.D.: South Dakota State Historical Society Press, 2006.
- Source 2: Morgan, George Robert, and Ronald R. Weedon. "Oglala Sioux Use of Medicinal Herbs." Great Plains Quarterly 10, no. 1 (1990): 18-35.
- Source 3: Neihardt, John G. Black Elk Speaks. Edited by Philip Joseph Deloria and Raymond J. DeMallie. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 2014.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: Walker, J. R. Lakota Society. Edited by Raymond J. DeMallie. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1982.
- Source 2: White Hat, Albert. Life's Journey - Zuya : Oral Teachings from Rosebud. Edited by John Cunningham. Salt Lake City: The University of Utah Press, 2012.
- Source 3: Wissler, Clark. "Societies and Ceremonial Associations in the Oglala Division of the Teton-Dakota." In Societies of the Plains Indians. New York: The Trustees, 1912.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: Paper, Jordan D. Offering Smoke : The Sacred Pipe and the Native American Religion. Moscow: University of Idaho Press, 1988.
- Source 2: Powers, William K. Oglala Religion. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1982.
- Source 3: Powers, William K. "Wiping the Tears: Lakota Religion in the Twenty-First Century." In Native Religions and Cultures of North America: Anthropology of the Sacred, edited by Lawrence Eugene Sullivan, 249 p. New York: Continuum, 2000.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: DeMallie, Raymond J, and Douglas R. Parks. "George A. Dorsey and the Development of Plains Indian Anthropology." In Anthropology, History, and American Indians: Essays in Honor of William Curtis

Sturtevant, edited by William L. Merrill and Ives Goddard. Washington, D.C.: Smithsonian Institution Press, 2002.

- Source 2: Densmore, Frances. Teton Sioux Music. Smithsonian Institution Bureau of Ethnology Bulletin 61. Washington, DC: Smithsonian Institution, 1916.
- Source 3: Dorsey, George A. "Legend of the Teton Sioux Medicine Pipe." *The Journal of American Folklore* 19, no. 75 (1906): 326-29.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: Amiotte, Arthur. "Eagles Fly Over." In *I Become Part of It : Sacred Dimensions in Native American Life*, edited by D. M. Dooling and Paul Jordan-Smith, 291 p. San Francisco: Harper, 1992.
- Source 2: Bucko, Raymond A. "Father Eugene Buechel's Collection of Lakota Materials." *Material Culture* 39, no. 2 (01/2007 2007): 17-42.
- Source 3: Bucko, Raymond A. *The Lakota Ritual of the Sweat Lodge : History and Contemporary Practice. Studies in the Anthropology of North American Indians*. Lincoln: Published by the University of Nebraska Press in Cooperation with the American Indian Studies Research Institute, Indiana University, Bloomington, 1998.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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- Source 2: Walker, J. R. *Lakota Belief and Ritual*. Edited by Raymond J. DeMallie and Elaine A. Jahner. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press.: Published in cooperation with the Colorado Historical Society, 1991.
- Source 3: Walker, J. R. *Lakota Myth*. Edited by Elaine Jahner. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1983.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: Lewis, Thomas H. *The Medicine Men : Oglala Sioux Ceremony and Healing. Studies in the Anthropology of North American Indians*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press in cooperation with the American Indian Studies Research Institute, Indiana University, 1990.
- Source 3: Matson, William B. *Crazy Horse : The Lakota Warrior's Life & Legacy*. First ed. Layton: Gibbs Smith, 2016.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: Elk, Black. *The Gift of the Sacred Pipe : Based on Black Elk's Account of the Seven Rites of the Oglala Sioux*. Edited by Joseph Epes Brown and Vera Louise Drysdale. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 1982.
- Source 2: Erdoes, Richard, and Alfonso Ortiz. *American Indian Myths and Legends*. Edited by Richard Erdoes and Alfonso Ortiz. 1st ed. New York: Pantheon Books, 1984.
- Source 3: Fire, John, ed. *Lame Deer, Seeker of Visions*. Edited by Richard Erdoes. New York: Simon and Schuster, 1972.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

- Source 1: *The Sixth Grandfather: Black Elk's Teachings Given to John G. Neihardt*. Edited by Raymond J.

DeMallie. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1984.

– Source 2: Smith, JL. "The Sacred Calf Pipe Bundle: It's Effect on the Present Teton Dakota." *Plains Anthropologist* 15, no. 48 (1970): 87-93.

– Source 3: Smith, JL. *A Short History of the Sacred Calf Pipe of the Teton Dakota*. Kendall Park: Lakota Books, 1994.

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Region: Lakota Reservations

– Source 1: Deloria, Ella Cara. *Waterlily*. Lincoln: University of Nebraska Press, 1988.

– Source 2: Deloria Jr., Vine. *The World We Used to Live In : Remembering the Powers of the Medicine Men*. Golden: Fulcrum Pub., 2006.

– Source 3: DeMallie, Raymond J, and Douglas R Parks. *Sioux Indian Religion : Tradition and Innovation*. Norman: University of Oklahoma Press, 1987.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fyb1OkRAVUs&t=368s>

– Source 1 Description: Lakota Emergence Narrative

– Source 2 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fyb1OkRAVUs&t=368s>

– Source 2 Description: Arvol Looking Horse on the White Buffalo Calf Woman and Prophecy

– Source 3 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/user/sdwolakota>

– Source 3 Description: Wo Lakota Project videos on Lakota culture, oral tradition, religion, and more

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: http://www.nativecairns.org/CAIRNS/Emergence_Narrative.html

– Source 1 Description: Lakota Emergence Narrative

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

General Variables

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are they written:

— Yes

Notes: Some of the oral tradition which serves as the basis for Lakota religious traditions has been recorded by various ethnographers and community members, however the majority of religious instruction and tradition is passed orally.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are they oral:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

— Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is the cultural contact competitive:

— Yes

Notes: Prior to the enactment of the American Indian Religious Freedom Act of 1978 (AIRFA), the practice of any American Indian religious tradition, Lakota or otherwise, was actively suppressed by the United States federal government. While this legislation sought to remedy interference of ceremonial traditions by federal agents, conflict still occurs in a number of ways. Firstly, despite the expansion of AIRFA in 1994 to protect access to sacred sites on federal lands, frequently within the confines of the National Parks and Forest Services, access to and ownership of the Black Hills in southwestern South Dakota is still a contentious subject. Originally allocated to the Očhéthi Šakówiŋ in the 1868 Fort Laramie Treaty, the Black Hills represent one of the most sacred locations in the Lakota landscape. The Black Hills exist as the birthplace of the Očhéthi Šakówiŋ as, per oral tradition, the location of the emergence of their ancestors onto this earth took place at Wind Cave. Since the government seizure of the Black Hills in 1877, access and ownership serves as a point of contention between many Lakota individuals and the federal government. The United States Supreme Court ruled in favor of the members of the Očhéthi Šakówiŋ in 1980,

but instead of returning ownership of the Black Hills, \$102 million was set aside as compensation. This money continues to be held in trust because many argue that the Black Hills were never for sale and taking this money would be congruent with selling one of their most sacred places. This is just one location where access issues continue to cause conflict between Lakota religious practitioners and the federal government. One other example is Mathó Tǎ́pila (Devil's Tower). Another example of conflict includes the continued destruction of Lakota ceremonial and burial locations. While the Native American Graves Protection and Repatriation Act of 1990 (NAGPRA) formally seeks to protect burial sites and return funerary objects and ancestral remains to American Indian communities, sites such as these continue to be destroyed. One key example includes sites that were in the proposed route for the Dakota Access Pipeline.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: Although monumental architecture in the Western sense is nonexistent in Lakota religious practice, during *Wiwáŋyąŋg Wačhípi* (Sundance) a cottonwood tree is cut down and erected in the center of the dance arbor, adorned with various ceremonial accoutrements, and serves as the central dance pole that dancers will be attached to during the ceremony.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Tombs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Cemeteries:

— No

Notes: Cemeteries in the Western sense have been adopted by many Lakota people, however traditional burial practices still take place. These include the construction of scaffolding for the deceased individual as well as a number of ceremonial prescriptions.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Temples:

— No

Notes: Large temples are not necessary for practitioners of Lakota religious traditions, however the sweat lodge itself is an important structure for the inipi ceremony.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Altars:

— Yes

Notes: A variety of different altars have been and continue to be constructed by contemporary Lakota peoples. Altars can vary based on the type of ceremony being conducted and the individual conducting said ceremony (see Lebeau 2009).

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Devotional markers:

— Yes

Notes: The most common devotional marker used in many ceremonies and frequently seen in the landscape are tobacco ties. These cloth bundles filled with tobacco are crafted as an offering during various ceremonies. Cloth is usually red, yellow, white, black, blue, or green and is filled with čhaŋšášá (red willow bark), traditional tobacco (*Nicotiana rustica*), or commercial tobacco (*Nicotiana tabacum*). They are often placed in trees and can also be used to designate ceremonial space when made as a garland.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

— No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: The two most common forms of religious architecture include the sweat lodge and the Sundance arbor.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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Region: Lakota Reservations

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

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Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

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Notes: Although monumental architecture in the Western sense is nonexistent in Lakota religious practice, during *Wiwányang Wačhípi* (Sundance) a cottonwood tree is cut down and erected in the center of the dance arbor, adorned with various ceremonial accoutrements, and serves as the central dance pole that dancers will be attached to during the ceremony.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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Region: Lakota Reservations

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: The two most common forms of religious architecture include the sweat lodge and the Sundance arbor.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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Region: Lakota Reservations

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Region: Lakota Reservations

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– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

How strict is pilgrimage:

– Optional (common)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Beliefs

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body.

Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Ní and šičúŋ

Notes: Ní is described as the breath of life, a spiritual essence that is evidence of being alive.

When an individual dies, this spiritual aspect leaves their body. All objects, animate and inanimate, also possess an immortal spiritual power known as šičúŋ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans’ behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts

and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Food:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Many may argue that the spiritual concept of Wakǎ́ŋ Tǎ́ŋka exists as a supreme deity for Lakota religious practitioners, however abundant evidence exists to suggest that this is primarily a misunderstanding by early ethnographers and Christian missionaries.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can reward:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can punish:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Through divination processes:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Most supernatural beings are understood as being organized into four categories further organized into four groups of categories (for a total of 16) referred to collectively as Wakǂáŋ Tháŋka.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In a human form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In animal/plant form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: An individual's *šičúŋ* is believed to be returned to the supernatural realm after death. Because of their immortal nature, *šičúŋ* of deceased spiritual leaders can be granted to living spiritual leaders to add to their personal spiritual power.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Cremation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Mummification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Burials in the reservation era largely resemble Western burial customs, but often include an extended wake period and community feeds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: Traditional Lakota burial traditions include the construction of a scaffold on which the body of the deceased is placed, however these types of burials became less and less common during the reservation era.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

–Yes [specify]: Wakes can last up to a period of four days and include a community feed that takes place for those in attendance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Notes: Objects deemed potentially useful for the journey to the spirit world are frequently interred with the deceased.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Notes: Oftentimes, a plate of food will be interred with the deceased to provide sustenance for the individual's spirit on its journey.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: Ní and šičúŋ

Notes: Ní is described as the breath of life, a spiritual essence that is evidence of being alive. When an individual dies, this spiritual aspect leaves their body. All objects, animate and inanimate, also possess an immortal spiritual power known as šičúŋ.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Reincarnation in this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In a human form:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In form of an inanimate object(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In non-individual form (i.e. some form of corporate rebirth, tribe, lineage. etc.):

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Reincarnation linked to notion of life-transcending causality (e.g. karma):

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other form of reincarnation in this world:

– Yes [specify]: An individual's *šičúŋ* is believed to be returned to the supernatural realm after death. Because of their immortal nature, *šičúŋ* of deceased spiritual leaders can be granted to living spiritual leaders to add to their personal spiritual power.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Cremation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Mummification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Interment:

– Yes

Notes: Burials in the reservation era largely resemble Western burial customs, but often include an extended wake period and community feeds.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Corpse is interred some other way:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Cannibalism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):

– Yes

Notes: Traditional Lakota burial traditions include the construction of a scaffold on which the body of the deceased is placed, however these types of burials became less and less common during the reservation era.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Feeding to animals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Secondary burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Wakes can last up to a period of four days and include a community feed that takes place for those in attendance.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Valuable items:

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

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Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

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Notes: Objects deemed potentially useful for the journey to the spirit world are frequently interred with the deceased.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

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Specific to this answer:

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Notes: Oftentimes, a plate of food will be interred with the deceased to provide sustenance for the individual's spirit on its journey.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are formal burials present:

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Specific to this answer:

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↳ As cenotaphs:

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Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

Notes: Many may argue that the spiritual concept of Wakǎ́ŋ Tǎ́ŋka exists as a supreme deity for Lakota religious practitioners, however abundant evidence exists to suggest that this is primarily a misunderstanding by early ethnographers and Christian missionaries.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can reward:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Through divination processes:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Only through specialists:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Only through monarch:
– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Communicate with living through other means:
– I don't know

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: Most supernatural beings are understood as being organized into four categories further organized into four groups of categories (for a total of 16) referred to collectively as Wakháŋ Thánka.

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:
Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Food:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: A part of certain ceremonies, it is common for certain participants to fast before or during these rituals. Two of these include *Wiwáŋyang Wačhípi* (Sundance) and *hanbléčheyapi* ("vision quest").

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Certain individuals participating in *Wiwáŋyang Wačhípi* (Sundance) are have their chests pierced and are tied to the dance pole in the center of the Sundance arbor. These individuals will dance until their piercings are pulled out resulting in chest wounds that are tended to using Lakota traditional ethnomedicine. Some practitioners may also have buffalo skulls attached to their backs in the same way which are then drug around the altar until they are pulled off. Still others may also be pierced in their arms with rawhide attached to eagle feathers that are then pulled out.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: This scarification, a result of *Wiwáŋyąŋ Wačhípi* (Sundance) participation, is not required, but is common.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Food taboos:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Hair:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Dress:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Ornaments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Archaic ritual language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: A part of certain ceremonies, it is common for certain participants to fast before or during these rituals. Two of these include *Wiwáŋyaŋg Wačhípi* (Sundance) and *haŋbléčheyapi* ("vision quest").

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– Yes

Notes: Certain individuals participating in *Wiwáŋyaŋg Wačhípi* (Sundance) are have their chests pierced and are tied to the dance pole in the center of the Sundance arbor. These individuals will dance until their piercings are pulled out resulting in chest wounds that are tended to using Lakota traditional ethnomedicine. Some practitioners may also have buffalo skulls attached to their backs in the same way which are then drug around the altar until they are pulled off. Still others may also be pierced in their arms with rawhide attached to eagle feathers that are then pulled out.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Tattoos/scarification:

– Yes

Notes: This scarification, a result of *Wiwáŋyaŋg Wačhípi* (Sundance) participation, is not required, but is common.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Circumcision:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Food taboos:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Hair:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Dress:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Ornaments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Archaic ritual language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Other:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Society and Institutions

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A sovereign American Indian nation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– Other [specify in comments]

Notes: A sovereign American Indian nation.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s)

other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is use of this distinct written language confined to religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Lakota Reservations